

Self-Image of Adolescents with Visible Disabilities in Buea Municipality

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Abstract

This study examined the self image of adolescents with visible disabilities in the Buea municipality southwest region of Cameroon. Adolescent is a pivotal stage in development where the formation of self concept is influenced by both internal experiences and external perceptions. For adolescents living with visible disabilities, this process is often shaped by societal attitude, and levels of social support. Using the descriptive survey research design, with closed and open-ended questionnaire 15 adolescents with visible disabilities were sampled for this study from two institutions, Government Bilingual Grammar School Molyko and Government Secondary School Buea. The findings indicated some adolescents demonstrated a strong and positive self image fostered by family support and inclusive school environments, while others experience diminished self-esteem due to bullying, marginalisation, lac of representation and overprotection. The study highlights the importance of inclusive policies, peer education and targeted psychosocial interventions to improve the self image and overall well-being of this vulnerable population.

Keywords: *Adolescents, Self-image, Visible disabilities.*

Introduction

Adolescence is a multifaceted developmental stage characterised by complex biological, cognitive, emotional, physical, and social changes. It is a transitional phase between childhood and adulthood often ranging from 10-19 years as classified by the world health organisation (WHO 2014). During this period individuals experience rapid physical development, cognitive shift, and emotional intensification, all of which contribute to the formation of identity and self concept. This stage presents an opportunity for growth and exploration, but it also poses great challenges including the development of a positive self image, mental health issues, influence of peers and the negotiation of independence from families. For adolescents with disabilities, this stage presents a unique opportunity for self discovery, social integration, and identity formation. They face more complex challenges in attaining developmental miles stones others will attain with minimal challenges, however some of them demonstrates great resilience, adaptive coping strategies and can form positive self-image despite societal barriers and stigma. Self image refers to an individual's perception of themselves, encompassing their physical appearance, abilities and emotional traits. The development of self image for adolescents with visible disabilities is complex due to the social and psychological challenges they face. Irrespective of the nature of a disabilities whether visible or invisible it can severely impact how individuals perceive themselves and are perceived by others. Most of them struggle with the task of discovering an identity that is separate from that of the individuals they associate with such as the family members and peers. This study seeks to understand how adolescents with disabilities perceives themselves how their self image is influenced by social, cultural and institutional factors and to provide insights that can guide efforts in improving the quality of life for these adolescents with disabilities.

Understanding Adolescence, Disabilities and Adolescent with Disabilities

Adolescence is fundamentally a biological phase, with the onset of puberty being the most obvious event. Puberty marks the period during which an individual's body undergoes a series of physical changes which are driven by hormonal fluctuations. This biological transformation typically occurs in stages and can vary in timing, leading to individual differences in adolescent experiences (Rosenfield, 2003). It is also a period of significant cognitive development which constitute a movement from concrete operational thinking to formal operational thinking, characterized by the ability to

think abstractly, logically, systematically, and the development of executive functions, such as planning, attention, and self-regulation. This cognitive shift allows adolescents to consider hypothetical scenarios, engage in complex problem-solving, and think about future possibilities (Piaget (1972), Best & Miller, 2010).

From the psychological and emotional stance, adolescents begin to form a clearer sense of identity and develop more complex emotional responses. Erikson (1968) proposed it is a stage of identity vs role confusion, where adolescents struggle to figure out who they are, what they believe in and where they fit in the world. It is a time of exploration, they experiment various roles, values and behaviours and if they successfully resolve this stage, they will build a strong sense of identity and a stable understanding of self. But if they fail, they experience role confusion feeling uncertain about their identity, and unsure of their place in the world. This often result in difficulty in making decisions, low self esteem and challenges in forming meaningful relationships (La Greca & Harrison, 2005). Cultural context and family dynamics are salient factors which shape adolescent development. Adolescents strive for greater independence, often leading to tension in family relationships as parents navigate the balance between offering guidance and granting autonomy. In some cultures, adolescence may be seen as a period of increased responsibility, with adolescents often expected to contribute to the family or community (Smetana, 2005).

The intersection of adolescence and disability impacts the social, emotional, self-discovery, social integration, and identity development of most adolescents with disabilities. They often face additional obstacles in achieving typical developmental milestones, such as academic achievement, peer relationships, and self-esteem development, however the degree of difficulty faced is to an extent determine by the type and severity of the disability (Norell & Bertilsson, 2014). Adolescents with physical disabilities, such as those on wheelchairs, prosthetics, or chronic health conditions, face challenges related to mobility, access to spaces, and physical activities which affect their body image. Body image in adolescence is crucial because it is a stage where appearance and physical capabilities are central to self-esteem (Grogan, 2006). Social acceptance, which is a key developmental concern in adolescence, is often hindered by societal stereotypes and stigmatization of individuals with visible disabilities, (Lindsay, 2011).

Disability is a complex concept due to its multiple definitions across various disciplines reflecting its multifaceted nature. The medical and biological disciplines hold that disability is a defect or impairment that resides within the individual and are seen as medical conditions that requires treatment or rehabilitation to normalise the person. They see disability as a physiological or psychological condition that disrupts an individual's ability to function (Glover, 2014). They completely shut out the place of environmental, social and psychological triggers to disabilities. Psychologically, disability is often studied in terms of the impact of impairments on an individual's mental health and emotional well-being. Persons with disabilities often experience social stigma, discrimination, and exclusion, which often lead to feelings of isolation, anxiety, and depression these negative experiences are often internalised by these individuals which eventually exacerbate their mental health challenge (Link & Phelan, 2001).

The social model holds that disability is a social construct and not an inherent trait which result from societal attitudes, structures, and policies that fail to accommodate diversity. It is shaped by the interactions between individuals and the environments in which they live. Social barriers, such as inaccessible buildings, negative attitudes, and limited employment opportunities, create disability by preventing individuals from participating fully in society. The social model argues that the transformation of the societal structures for equal participation and access for all regardless of impairments rather than changing the individual is the best way to address disabilities (Oliver, 1990).

The biopsychosocial model introduced by the World Health Organisation (WHO 2001) holds that disability is an interaction between an individual's health condition and contextual factors such as physical barriers, biological and social environment which include attitudes, and access to resources. Through the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF) they established that disability includes:

- Impairments which are problems in body function or structure
- Activity limitations which are difficulties in performing tasks
- Participation restrictions which are problems in involvement in life situations (WHO, 2011).

Disabilities are categorised into two broad groups, visible and invisible disabilities. Visible disabilities are physical sensory or cognitive impairments that are noticeable or apparent to others, they can be seen or observed without needing any specialised equipment or testing. These disabilities often affect an individual's appearance, mobility, or ability to perform certain tasks, and they can range from mild to profound. The concept of visible disabilities encompasses various conditions, and it can significantly influence how individuals are perceived, how they interact with others and how they navigate daily life. Invisible disabilities on the other hand refers to a range of conditions that are not immediately apparent to others. These disabilities can affect a person's ability to function in various aspects of life such as work, school, or social interaction but they are not outwardly seen. Due to their invisible nature, they are often misunderstood or overlooked, which can lead to challenges such as lack of accommodations, stigma and difficulty in gaining recognition and support (Glover, 2014).

Most visible disabilities are characterised by physical conditions that affects a person's ability to move, dexterity and ability to perform physical tasks such as; amputations, cerebral palsy which is neurological condition that affect muscle coordination and body movement, spinal cord injuries which often result in paralysis or other mobility limitations and often result in the use of wheelchairs, braces or other assistive devices, muscular dystrophy (muscle weakness and loss). It is also characterised by sensory impairments such as visual impairment including blindness or low vision which require mobility aid like white cane or the use of guide dog. There is however certain cognitive impairment with physical symptoms such as Down Syndrome with noticeable facial features and behaviour traits that makes them qualify as visible disabilities (Gorib et al., 2022).

As conditions that are apparent to others through physical appearance or behavior, they have as key characteristic observable without requiring any special knowledge or diagnostic tests and it impact an adolescent's self image, and often lead to difficulties in communication, problem-solving, and academic achievement (Schalock et al., 2007). Visible disabilities often expose individuals to stereotypes and prejudices, marginalisation, identity struggles as they navigate the pressures of conforming to social norms which may result in challenges with self acceptance.

Visible disabilities often lead to judgments based on appearance, which can result in people being treated differently and result in exclusion, accessibility to community services such as health care, education or employment opportunities that accommodate their needs is difficult if not impossible. However, supportive environment enables them to thrive in every domain of life. The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), adopted by the United Nations in 2006, framed disability as a human rights issue and emphasizes the need for inclusion, accessibility and equal treatment. It advocates for the removal of barriers that prevent individuals from fully participating in society and affirms the right to education, employment, health care, and social integration (UN, 2006). However, challenges remain in fully implementing legal protections and ensuring accessibility in all aspects of life.

According to the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF) an estimated 1.3 billion people, 16% of the global population are currently experiencing significant disabilities and that disability affects 10% of every population (children, youths, adult and the aged), with an estimate of 200 million adolescents. These adolescents face challenges ranging from access to rehabilitation and health, education and employment, practices and cultural beliefs, negative perception and physical barriers to inability to build a positive self image (WHO, 2018).

Adolescents with disabilities often experience difficulties in developing a clear sense of identity and positive self image because they face barriers that others might not. Some of them struggle with social integration, stigma, or physical limitation. Social acceptance is one of the most important developmental milestones during adolescence. For adolescents with disabilities, building friendships and maintaining relationships is more challenging due to social exclusion, difficulties fitting in, or the stigma associated with disability which often result in inability to establish a strong sense of self. The desire to fit in and be accepted by peers might conflict with their unique needs or physical differences making the process of self-discovery more challenging which can contribute to emotional distress and lower quality of life (Carter et al., 2009).

The family and cultural context of adolescent with disabilities play a significant role in shaping their identity. Supportive families and communities enable them to navigate their disabilities positively fostering a sense of pride and resilience. However, in some cases family members may have unrealistic expectations, overprotectiveness or internalised stigma which results in feelings of inadequacy and identity confusion in the adolescent (Norell & Bertilsson, 2014).

Most adolescents are undergoing an intense time of body-consciousness and self-evaluation. Body image, or how an adolescent perceives their physical appearance, is crucial to their self-esteem and overall self-concept. Adolescents with physical disabilities or visible impairments may develop negative body image due to societal ideals of beauty and physical ability. Negative body image can lead to low self-esteem, poor mental health, and an increased risk of developing eating disorders or engaging in risky behaviours. Adolescents with disabilities often face a complex relationship with body image as they try to navigate social expectations while coping with physical limitations (Grogan, 2006).

Development of self image

McLeod, (2008) holds that, self-image refers to how we see ourselves on a more global level, both internally and externally self-image as “the idea, conception, or mental image one has of oneself” Self-image and self concept are strongly associated, but they're not quite the same thing. Self-concept is a more overarching construct than self-image: it involves how you see yourself, how you think about yourself, and how you feel about yourself. In a sense, self-image is one of the components that make up self-concept. Similarly, self-image has a lot to do with self-esteem. After all, how we see ourselves is a big contributing factor to how we feel about ourselves.

It could be said that self-image is a complex and multifaceted concept, as a psychological construct, it refers to how individuals perceive themselves. It encompasses an individual's beliefs, attitudes, and perceptions about their physical appearance, abilities, personality traits, and social identity, and has profound implications on an individual's behaviour, social interaction, mental health and overall well-being. It is shaped by a combination of internal factors such as cognitive processes, emotional regulation and external influences such as family, culture, societal standards (Carter et al., 2009). Self-image can be broken down into several components, including Physical Self-Image, which refers individual's perception of their own body and appearance and constitute aspects like body size, shape, weight, and attractiveness. Social Self-Image which encompasses how individuals perceive their social identity such as their interactions, social roles, and perceived acceptance in different social contexts. Psychological Self-Image which involves an individual's self-perception of their cognitive abilities, emotional states, personality traits, and overall mental functioning. The most significant influence on self image and well-being is the gap between one's "ideal self" that is how they wish to be and their "actual self" how they perceive themselves as stipulated by Carl Rogers (1959).

According to Cagliostro, (2018) & Oltmann, (2014), there are six dimensions of self image, which include Physical dimension: (how a person evaluates his or her appearance), psychological dimension (how a person evaluates his or her personality) intellectual dimension (how a person evaluates his or her intelligence), skills dimension (how a person evaluates his or her social and technical skills), moral dimension (how a person evaluates his or her values and principles), sexual dimension (how a person feels he or she fits into society's masculine/feminine norms). Oltmann, (2014), states that, a positive self-image is having a good view of yourself, such as; seeing yourself as an attractive and desirable person, having an image of yourself as a smart and intelligent person, seeing a happy, healthy person when you look in the mirror, believing that you are at least somewhat close to your ideal version and thinking about how others perceive you.

Cagliostro, (2018) elucidates that a negative self-image is the flipside of the above and constitute: seeing oneself as unattractive and undesirable, having an image of oneself as a stupid or unintelligent person, seeing an unhappy, unhealthy person when they look in the mirror, believing that they are nowhere near to their ideal version, thinking that others perceive them as all of the above. He states that, poor self image leads to: Body Dysmorphic Disorder (BDD), depression, camouflaging (with body position, clothing, makeup, hair, hats, etc.), comparing body part to others' appearance, seeking surgery, checking in a mirror, avoiding mirrors, skin picking, excessive grooming, excessive exercise, changing clothes excessively, having an unstable or dysfunctional self-image or a distorted sense of self (how one feels about one's self), difficulty feeling empathy for others, feelings of isolation, boredom, and emptiness, a persistent fear of abandonment and rejection, including extreme emotional reactions to real and even perceived abandonment, history of unstable relationships that can change drastically from intense love and idealization to intense hate, intense changeable moods that can last for several days or for just a few hours, strong feelings of anxiety, worry, and depression, impulsive, risky, self-destructive and dangerous behaviours, including reckless driving, drug or alcohol abuse, and having unsafe sex, hostility, and instable career plans, goals, and aspirations.

Tajfel & Turner (1979) posits that people's perception of themselves, and others is based on their membership in various social groups. Group members influence people's behaviour, attitude and perceptions of themselves. Categorisation into various social groups can be term naturalistic such as gender, race, nationality or profession. Once this categorisation is done individuals begin to adopt the norms, values and behaviours of that group and most often align their self concepts with the group's identity. This process often leads to the creation of in-group (those who belong) and out group (those who do not belong,) and this give rise to social comparison, ingroup favouritism and outgroup bias which often leads to prejudices, stereotypes and discrimination. It is worth noting that an individual's self image is tied to the status and success of their in-group. When the group is positively rated members' self-image is enhanced. Conversely when the group is negatively rated it gives rise to lower individual self image. This theory has implications on how persons with disabilities perceive themselves and are perceived by others. Persons with disabilities often form an in-group based on their shared experiences and challenges. By identifying with a group of people who share similar disabilities or experiences individuals can foster a sense of belonging and solidarity which can contribute positively to their self image. Being part of an in-group provide social support helps counteract isolation and offers validation of their experiences. McLaughlin (2014) holds that comparison of ingroup to outgroup for persons with disabilities against persons without disabilities can negatively affect their self image. If society holds a biased view that people with disabilities are less capable, it will give rise to low self esteem, the internalisation of such societal comparisons easily undermines confidence and identity. But positive societal comparison such as celebrating achievements shared struggles and mutual support bolster the self-esteem and builds a strong positive disability identity and affirms a sense of self-worth creating a more positive self-image.

Thus, for persons with disabilities, their identity is influenced by both the personal characteristics associated with their disability and the way society views disability. Disabling conditions can lead to stigmatization, which can profoundly impact self-image, as individuals internalize societal biases. Tajfel & Turner (1979) highlights that for persons with disabilities group identification with others who share similar experiences can lead to social support and the formation of

positive disability identity which strengthens self-esteem. However, marginalisation and negative social comparisons to non-disabled groups can harm self image.

Carl Rogers' (1959) humanistic theory emphasized the importance of congruence between the actual self and ideal self in developing a healthy self-image. Individuals with disabilities may experience incongruence if they feel that their disability prevents them from achieving their ideal self. Discrepancies may also arise between their actual abilities and the idealized abilities society holds for all individuals, leading to negative self-image or feelings of inadequacy. Inconsistent feedback from others, such as being treated differently or receiving pity, may also negatively affect their self-esteem. Rogers, central tenet of unconditional positive regards points that an individual thrive when they are accepted and valued by others without judgement or conditions. Receiving unconditional positive regards for an adolescent with disabilities from a significant other such as family members, teachers and peers is critical in building a positive self image. Acceptance helps persons with disability integrate their disability into their identity without feeling any sense of shame or inadequacy. Rogers holds that individuals are likely to develop a positive self image especially when they feel authentic and true to themselves rather than trying to meet external expectations. Fostering an environment where adolescent with disabilities can be authentic embracing both their abilities and disabilities helps reduce feelings of shame or adequacy. Adolescents with disabilities will develop positive self image where they are listened to empathetically this is an atmosphere where their experiences, challenges and emotions are understood and validated. It reduces feelings of isolation and self doubt and encourages adolescent to embrace their authentic selves. This theory calls for the questioning of societal norms that defines success based on able-bodied standards, and individualised definition, flexible and inclusive view of success. From the theoretical stance it is evident that it is not disability per se but the contextual, social, physical, and emotional dimensions of the impact of disability perception that may influence self-image.

Implications of the Disability Identity Model by Tom Shakespeare, (2006) on self image

Understanding self image of persons with disability warrants a comprehension of the stages of identity formation for persons with disability. According to Shakespeare (2006) model, disability is not just a medical or functional condition but also a social and cultural identity that can be understood in the context of personal experience, societal attitudes, and broader political frameworks. To him, persons with disabilities form their identity through the following stages:

Personal Identity and Social Identity: Shakespeare's model suggests that both personal and social aspects of identity influence how individuals perceive themselves and are perceived by others. He defines personal identity as an individual's understanding and how he or she relates to their disability and social identity as how society views and categorizes individuals with disabilities. Thus, the model suggests that the way people with disabilities integrate these aspects shapes their overall sense of identity.

Stages of Disability Identity Development: persons with disability whether congenital or adventitious go through different stages in their understanding of their disability and their place in society. These stages can include:

- **Pre-Disability Awareness:** Before the onset of disability, individuals have little or no understanding of disability identity. Disability, at this stage is an abstract concept.
- **Awareness and Adaptation:** As individuals come to terms with the presence of a disability, they may initially experience a period of adjustment. This could involve feelings of loss or grief, as they struggle with societal barriers and the personal implications of the disability. Adolescents who go through the stages of awareness, adaptation, and empowerment are more likely to accept their disability and feel confident in their abilities, rather than seeing themselves as incomplete or defective. This acceptance helps build a positive self-image, as they understand that their disability does not define their worth or potential.
- **Acceptance and Integration:** Over time, individuals with disabilities may move toward acceptance, integrating their disability into their identity. This stage often involves the development of a proud disability identity, where the disability is not seen as a deficiency but as a part of their whole self. Individuals may reject the stigmatized, medicalized views of disability and embrace a social model of disability.
- **Empowerment and Advocacy:** This final stage involves advocacy and social change, where individuals recognize their ability to influence public attitudes and systems. In this phase, individuals with disabilities may work toward political activism, promoting inclusion, rights, and equal opportunities.

A significant aspect of Shakespeare's model is the exploration of stigma which he defines as negative societal attitudes toward individuals with disabilities. The way society views disability greatly affects how individuals with disabilities develop their own sense of self. Shakespeare argues that stigma can be internalized, leading to feelings of shame or inadequacy in people with disabilities. However, a key feature of developing a positive disability identity involves resisting stigma and challenging negative societal norms. Adolescents with disabilities who engage in self-advocacy and disability pride are better equipped to combat internalized stigma and social exclusion. Overcoming societal stereotypes can greatly improve self-esteem and help adolescents feel more accepted and validated in their communities. Developing

a positive self-image is not just about personal acceptance but also about societal acceptance and creating a more inclusive world.

He holds that as individuals progress through the stages of self-awareness, adaptation, and acceptance, they internalize a positive view of their disability. This self-affirmation, where disability is embraced as part of a rich and complex identity, contributes to higher self-esteem and self-respect and a realisation that disability is just one part of an individual's identity, not something that defines them entirely. By seeing themselves as multifaceted individuals, adolescents and adults with disabilities can integrate their disability into their broader identity, which leads to a more holistic and balanced sense of self.

Shakespeare's Disability Identity Model has profound implications for the development of a positive self-image among individuals with disabilities. By promoting acceptance, empowerment, and resistance to stigma, the model encourages individuals to embrace their disability as an integral part of their identity. This acceptance leads to greater self-confidence, improved mental health, and a stronger sense of self-worth. Also, the model emphasizes the importance of social support, community engagement, and advocacy, all of which reinforces a positive self-image. Through these mechanisms, individuals with disabilities can foster a sense of pride, dignity, and empowerment that transcends societal stereotypes and contributes to a fulfilling and meaningful life. Building a positive self-image for adolescents with disabilities is a complex and multifaceted process, influenced by various personal, social, and cultural factors. The process involves recognizing and embracing disability as part of one's identity, rather than viewing it as a limitation or deficit. Shakespeare's Disability Identity Model offers valuable insights into how adolescents with disabilities can build a positive self-image by encouraging them to navigate their disability identity with confidence, resist societal stigma, and embrace empowerment.

Statement of the problem

It is expected that every adolescent irrespective of their nature should have a positive self image which comprise of having a healthy and realistic perception of oneself, recognising and valuing one's strength, accepting one's flaws and feeling confident in one's abilities and worth as a person. This is often developed through social acceptance and participation in everyday activities in school, work, and other social events which result in the development of a sense of inner peace, respect, success, self worth, confidence, emotional resilience and more. However, this is not the case for most adolescents with disabilities in the Buea Municipality, as they face unique challenges that influence their self-image and overall wellbeing. Despite advancement in disability rights and inclusion, these individuals often struggle with social stigma, limited access to education, inadequate healthcare and societal attitudes that marginalises them. These significantly impact their self-esteem, sense of identity and how they perceive themselves in relation to their peers.

Although significant efforts have been made to integrate and include them to the mainstream society, there is a lack of comprehensive studies that specifically addresses the self-image of this group in the Cameroonian context. As a result, the emotional and psychological aspects of their development particularly in relation to societal perceptions and personal self worth remain underexplored. Understanding the self worth and factors that shape the self-image of adolescent with disabilities is essential for developing targeted interventions that foster greater inclusion, empowerment and mental wellbeing for these individuals. This study aims to investigate how adolescents with disabilities perceive themselves and how their self image is influenced by social, cultural and institutional factors and to provide insights that can guide efforts in improving the quality of life for these adolescents with disabilities.

Objective of the study

This study sought to investigate how adolescent with visible disabilities perceive themselves and how social, cultural and institutional factors influenced their self-image.

Research question

The study had the following research question

- How does adolescent with visible disabilities perceive themselves?
- How does social, cultural and institutional factors influence the self image of adolescents with disabilities?

Research methodology

Through the descriptive survey design and the purposive sampling technique, a total sample of 15 adolescents with visible disabilities were selected for this study from two institutions, Government Bilingual Grammar School Molyko and Government Secondary School Buea Town, as such the following types of disabilities were sampled visual, Physical and hearing impairments. The study made used of a blend of instrument: the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale which is a 10-item scale that measures global self-worth by measuring both positive and negative feelings about the self. The scale is believed to be unidimensional. All items are answered using a 4-point Likert scale format ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. In addition to the scale an open-ended question was added to ascertain facts on the impact of social,

cultural and institution on the self image of adolescents with disabilities which could not be expressed on the scale. Thus, the study sampled was as follows:

Table1: Description of sample

Disability Types	Gender		Age	
	M	F	11-14	15-20
Visual impairment	04	02	02	04
Physical impairment	04	00	02	02
Hearing impairment	02	03	01	04
Subtotal	10	05	05	10
Grand total	15			

Table one indicates that a total of fifteen students with disabilities were sampled for the study with the following category of disabilities, visual impairment (06), physical impairment (04), and hearing impairment (05). Among the students sampled ten (10) were males and five (05) were females, five (05) of them were within the age bracket of eleven to fourteen (11-14) and ten (10) were within the age bracket of fifteen to twenty (15-20).

Table 2: Adolescents with Visible Disabilities' Perception of Themselves

SN	ITEMS	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree
1	Overall, I am satisfied with myself.	5	5		5
2	At times I think I am no good at all.	1	8	6	
3	I feel that I have several good qualities.	8	6	1	
4	I can do things as well as most other people.	5	4	3	3
5	I feel I do not have much to be proud of.	5		5	5
6	I certainly feel useless at times.	8	5	1	1
7	I feel that I'm a person of worth, at least on an equal plane with others.	8	3	3	1
8	I wish I could have more respect for myself.	4	7	2	2
9	All in all, I am inclined to feel that I am a failure.	3	5	2	5
10	I take a positive attitude toward myself.	5	4	2	4

The table above brings out the perception of adolescents with visible disabilities about themselves. Out of the fifteen respondents five (05) strongly agreed to the fact that they were satisfied with themselves which implies a strong positive self image. Five (05) of them agreed which also signify a positive self image. Five (05) of them disagreed to the fact that they are satisfied with themselves. This implies that they are not satisfied with themselves which connotes a negative self image. One (01) person strongly agreed and eight (08) agreed to the fact that they sometimes think they were not good at all, the implication is a negative self image. While six (06) strongly disagreed to the fact implying they have a strong positive self image. Eight (08) respondents strongly agreed and six (06) agreed that they feel that they have several good qualities implying a positive self image while just one (01) respondent strongly agreed that they were not having several good qualities implying a negative self image. As far as the item on seeing oneself capable of doing things as others is concerned, five (05) of the respondents strongly agreed, four (04) agreed, three (03) strongly disagreed and three (03) disagreed. Five (05) respondents strongly agreed that they felt they do not have much to be proud of, while five (05) strongly disagreed and five (05) disagreed. This connotes a negative self image for the five who strongly agreed and a positive self image for the ten who strongly agreed and agreed. Eight (08) of the participants strongly agreed that they feel useless at certain point and five (05) also agreed implying a negative self image while one (01) strongly disagreed and one (01) disagreed connoting a positive self image. The table also indicates that eight (08) respondents strongly agreed and three (03) agreed that they persons of worth on equal plane with others connoting a positive self image while three (03) strongly disagreed and one (01) disagreed to the fact connoting a negative self image. Four (04) respondents strongly agreed to the fact that they wish they could have more respect for themselves, seven (07) also agreed implying that they have a poor self image while two (02) strongly disagreed and two (02) simply disagreed connoting a positive self image. As far as rating themselves whether they feel they are failures or not three (03) strongly agreed that they were, five (05) simply agreed connoting a negative self image while two (02) strongly disagreed and five (05) simply disagree implying a positive self image. Five (05) strongly agreed to the fact that they take a positive attitude towards themselves, four (04) simply agreed signifying a positive self image while two (02) strongly disagreed and four (04) simply disagreed connoting a negative self image. It could be concluded that persons with visible disabilities, indicated items on that scale that depicts they have both positive and negative perception of themselves.

Table 3: Qualitative findings on self image perception of Adolescents with Visible Disabilities

Type of perception	Themes and explanation	Quotes
Positive self perception	Resilience and Strength: Determination which lead to a sense of pride in overcoming challenges	“My disability is my strength, and it is never a problem to me”
	Sense of Uniqueness: individual identity, unique perspective which help them develop a strong sense of individual identity.	“I know I am different from others, and this makes me work hard to be the best”
	Sense of Achievement: academic achievements which boost their confidence and sense of competence	
	Independence and Autonomy: Having positive, accepting friends and family helps adolescents feel valued and respected, enhancing their self-esteem.	“I was the one who selected my friends and anyone who does not treat me well I report to school authorities”
Negative self perception	Feelings of Inferiority: feel less capable leading to low self-esteem.	“I have classmates who do not like to join me in doing assignment sometimes it makes me feel very bad, and most often I stay away from them.”
	Social Isolation: social exclusion or bullying, which can lead to feelings of loneliness and alienation, viewing themselves as inadequate or less valuable.	
	Fear of Rejection: fear being judged or rejected by their peers, leading to anxiety and a diminished sense of self-worth.	“Sometimes I stay in class during break and during some club activities because I don’t want my school mates making fun of me”
	Dependence and Helplessness: feel overly dependent on others for daily tasks accommodations.	

The following were identified as themes emanating from the open-ended questions. From the positive stance some adolescents with disability view themselves as having strength, resilience, and determination, leading to a sense of pride in overcoming challenges. Some says they are unique, their disability gives them a unique perspective, helping them develop a strong sense of individual identity. Also, some carry a strong sense of achievement and the successful management of their disability, academic achievements, or personal goals boost their confidence and sense of competence. It was also realised that most of them demonstrate a sense of independence and autonomy especially when given opportunities to make their own choices and navigate challenges, adolescents with disabilities develop a strong sense of independence and self-worth.

Despite these positive attributes some of them however, some of them still demonstrated certain negative self perception, feelings of Inferiority: Some adolescents feel less capable when compared to their peers due to the visible nature of their disability, leading to low self-esteem. They also demonstrated social isolation tendencies. Adolescents with visible disabilities experience bullying, which often lead to feelings of loneliness and alienation. They further state that negative attitudes or stereotypes about disability demonstrated by some teachers and classmates makes them feel inadequate or less valuable. Some hold that they fear being rejected by teachers and peers due to their disabilities and that they are often anxious when they are around some of their friends and teachers who do not like them and always make them feel down and less human, inadequate or a belief that they do not measure up. Some indicated that due to the nature of their disabilities they sometimes feel they are overly dependent on others for daily tasks and accommodation which leads to a perception of being incapable or less independent.

How does social, cultural and institutional factors influence their self image?

- Social factors have a profound impact on the self-image of adolescents with disabilities. These factors as identified include interactions with peers, family dynamics, societal attitudes, and the broader social environment in which these adolescents live. The following social factors were identified, and their impact indicated by respondents as follows

Theme	Explanation	Codes
Peer Interactions and	Spending time with family,	<i>“Encouragement from educators and</i>

Social Acceptance	friends and in most social events can positively or negatively impact adolescents with disabilities by building a positive identity, making them feel valued, provide emotional supports, build their resilience and thus enhance self image	<i>classmates creates an atmosphere where I feel valued and capable.”</i> <i>“Positive relationships with family, friends, and peers provide emotional support, builds a positive my self-esteem and resilience in me”.</i>
Social Integration and Inclusion	Interaction with peers, community involvement, group involvement	<i>“Involvement in community activities helps me build a positive identity and I also feel valued but discrimination, teasing, and exclusion by peers due to our disability often lead to feelings of inferiority and social rejection, loneliness”.</i> <i>when integrated and included into different aspects in the society I develop a sense of belonging, confidence, valued, improved self worth, normalises disabilities challenges, builds a sense of advocacy, personal growth and skill development.</i>
Family Support and Expectations	Family positive reinforcement,	<i>“Family support provides a sense of security, validation and acceptance, and helps me navigate our challenges which fosters boost my confidence and self worth”.</i> <i>“My Family set very high standards which leads to stress, anxiety and eventually result in lower self esteem when I fail to meet their expectations. Most often conflicting family expectations creates confusion about our identity which negatively impact our self image. Most family love is tied to achievements this often leaves us with limited self worth and causes feelings of worthlessness and give rise to comparison and competition among siblings”.</i>

Cultural factors significantly influence how adolescents with disabilities perceive themselves, this is because cultural attitudes, values, and beliefs shape the way disability is understood and experienced in society. In cultures where disabilities are accepted and view as a natural part of life promote self-acceptance and pride in one’s identity. Also, cultural practices that value diversity and inclusion boost our self-esteem by making us feel respected and valued. The adolescents identified that the following cultural factors impact their self image:

Language: *“some people express positive language towards disabilities expressed by members of my community makes me feel accepted, valued and confident but there are others who only see me as a burden, curse, and punishment and this makes me feel ashamed of who I am and often I will avoid going where they are”.*

“Words that emphasises ability reinforces my dignity and self esteem as it helps me see myself as “a whole” not being defined by my disability. Positive feedback especially from my teachers and parents often help me develop a healthy self image”.

“Derogatory words, labels, abuses, pitying languages such as saying “poor thing” including jokes or casual remarks as well as using tones that depict pity hurts deeply and makes me feel ashamed”

“When people talk about me rather than talk to me, when I am not included in a conversation happening in my presence makes me feel invisible and sometimes unwanted”.

Customs: *“Some people and families in my community practice over protection and this provide me with emotional support, which helps me embrace my disability as part of who I am, and the unconditional love and support I receive from them foster a strong sense of belonging and self-worth. Sincerely if I am succeeding today is because my achievements are always celebrated, and this encourages and empower me and makes me feel confident”.*

Norms: *“some people in my community see me as spiritually gifted and this has a positive and a negative impact on my self image, positively some people in my community celebrate me and see me as having a special and unique purpose and they respect me for that whereas others see me as a witch and they run away from me which makes me feel lonely and inferior as my words are often questioned.”*

In a nutshell cultural factor can either be a bridge or a barrier and makes adolescents with visible disabilities feel respected, empowered and accepted or marginalised and defined by their limitations.

Institutional factors are systems, structures and policies created by institutions in our case schools which influence peoples’ opportunities and rights and daily lives. Such can either support or hinder the development of a positive self-concept for adolescents with disabilities, affecting their overall well-being, self-esteem, and sense of belonging. Positive institutional environments that provide support, inclusion, and equitable opportunities foster a sense of competence, belonging, and self-worth in adolescents with disabilities. The following institutional factors were identified to influence the self image of adolescents with visible disabilities: first being educational systems such as the curriculum, accessibility of the school, and availability of special educational services and secondly the school policies. The adolescent declared the following.

Educational systems and policies: *“I attend a mainstream school and sometimes I am given appropriate support which fosters a sense of belonging, competence, and equality with other peers. Sometimes I am given adequate access to specialized services like assistive technology, and this helps me succeed in my exams and builds my self-confidence”.*

“When my school implement practices that promote equality and protect against discrimination it enhances my sense of worth and when I see older individuals with disabilities in various institutions occupying offices and other positions of responsibility like in school leadership, teaching I get inspire and motivated”.

Opportunities for participation in sports, arts, and other activities increases my ability for social integration and foster a positive self-image. Having supportive educators and mentors such as teachers and principals who encourage and believe in me contribute to my sense of competence and self-esteem.

Despite the benefits enjoyed by adolescents with disabilities from the positive institutional factors there are still negative institutions factors that impact their self image such as segregation:

“My school is a mainstream school, but I belong to a class where all students with disabilities are placed in one class and most often the class is referred to as “the disabled class this create feelings of exclusion, rejected, and reinforces a sense of being different”.

“Sometimes the support I receive is insufficient and the accommodative practices seem as though I am only begging for them. The absence and limited nature of these necessary accommodations especially physical access to offices, toilets, certain classrooms, inadequate and sometimes the lack of provision of additional minutes during exams, inadequate assistive devices often lead to frustration, feelings of inadequacy, and sometimes I even perform below my capacity and even fail”.

“I sometimes suffer from institutional discrimination which constitute low expectations, biased attitudes from educators and peers this often result in feeling undervalued and incapable and, the lack of physical accessibility such as ramps, and elevators in schools as well as other public spaces contribute to the feelings of frustration, exclusion, and limited opportunities”.

“The absent and limited access to necessary healthcare services and therapies in my school hinder my growth and wellbeing which reinforce feelings of helplessness and dependency”.

Discussions of Findings

Objective One: Perception of Self Image for adolescents with visible disabilities

Adolescence is a critical period for identity development, and for adolescents with disabilities, the process of shaping a self-image can be particularly challenging. The experience of having a disability, especially one that is visible, can significantly influence how an adolescent perceives themselves. The study found that most adolescents with visible disabilities have a mixture of both positive and negative self-image, however for most of them the negative in certain aspects like feeling worthless, not being proud of themselves, feeling useless at times, not having any form of self

satisfaction, and more. These findings are justified by Phelan (2001) who explained that stigma occurs when individuals are devalued based on characteristics that are perceived as different or inferior. One of the primary contributors to negative self-image in adolescents with disabilities is societal stigma and discrimination. Adolescents with disabilities often face prejudiced attitudes, which can lead to the internalization of negative stereotypes about their abilities and worth. Adolescents with disabilities are frequently subjected to societal stereotypes that view them as weak, dependent, or less capable, which can lead to feelings of inadequacy and inferiority (Dovidio et al., 2010). These negative societal attitudes often become internalized, which adversely affects adolescents' self-esteem. The visible nature of some disabilities may exacerbate the stigma, as individuals with visible disabilities are often more readily identified as different. Goffman (1963) coined the term "spoiled identity" to describe how individuals with visible disabilities are often judged primarily by their disability, which can overshadow other aspects of their personality. For many adolescents, this experience of being "othered" can lead to feelings of social exclusion, bullying, and loneliness, all of which can undermine their self-image (Schwartz et al., 2014).

Also, Peer interactions are central to the development of self-esteem during adolescence. However, for adolescents with disabilities, negative peer interactions can significantly impact their self-image. Research indicates that adolescents with disabilities often experience social exclusion, bullying, and teasing from their peers (Parker et al., 2016). This exclusion can be particularly harmful because adolescents are at an age where peer acceptance is a key factor in shaping self-worth. According to McLaughlin (2014), adolescents with disabilities who experience bullying or social isolation often report lower levels of self-esteem and higher levels of anxiety and depression. These negative peer interactions contribute to a sense of being inferior, different, or unworthy, which can lead to a negative self-image.

Family support plays a significant role in the development of self-image. For adolescents with disabilities, the way their families respond to their disability can have a profound effect on their self-esteem. Adolescents whose families are less accepting or view the disability as a burden may internalize these negative views, which can reinforce feelings of shame and low self-worth (Griffiths et al., 2017). Additionally, parents who do not encourage independence or self-advocacy may limit the adolescent's opportunities to develop confidence and self-esteem, leading to a negative self-image (Cohen & Davis, 2009).

Despite the fleet of negative perception exhibited by adolescents with visible disabilities, however they also portray certain positive traits such as feeling they have several good qualities, being able to do as others, feeling they are people of worth. Rutter (2012) holds that despite the challenges associated with having a disability, many adolescents develop resilience and coping strategies that contribute to a positive self-image. Resilience, defined as the ability to adapt positively to adversity, is a key factor in the development of self-esteem for adolescents with disabilities. He stipulates that resilient adolescents can manage stress and overcome challenges in ways that foster a sense of mastery and personal growth. For example, adolescents who develop strong coping mechanisms, such as seeking support from others, focusing on their strengths, and engaging in problem-solving, tend to report higher levels of self-esteem (Zimmerman, 2013). Self-advocacy is an important coping skill that can lead to a positive self-image. Tewksbury and VanderVen (2015) found that adolescents with disabilities who actively advocate for themselves, set goals, and engage in decision-making about their lives have a greater sense of autonomy and control, which improves their self-esteem. This sense of control allows adolescents to view themselves as capable and empowered, even in the face of challenges related to their disability.

While negative peer interactions can harm self-esteem, positive peer relationships can have the opposite effect. Adolescents with disabilities who experience acceptance and inclusion from their peers are more likely to develop a positive self-image. Elliott et al. (2016) argue that supportive peer relationships provide a sense of belonging, which is critical for building self-esteem during adolescence. Inclusive peer interactions help to normalize the disability and encourage adolescents to see themselves as valuable members of their social groups. Adolescents who are accepted by their peers are less likely to internalize negative stereotypes and are more likely to develop a positive self-concept.

Family support is essential for fostering a positive self-image in adolescents with disabilities. Families that are accepting, encouraging, and supportive of the adolescent's disability help them develop a strong sense of self-worth. Jolly and O'Shea (2018) emphasize that when families provide an environment that promotes independence, encourages self-advocacy, and fosters open communication, adolescents with disabilities are more likely to develop a positive self-image. Additionally, parents who model positive attitudes toward disability and promote self-acceptance help adolescents build resilience and confidence (Cohen & Davis, 2009).

A key aspect of positive self-image in adolescents with disabilities is the ability to integrate their disability into their overall sense of identity. When adolescents can accept their disability as a part of who they are, rather than as something that defines them entirely, they are more likely to develop a positive self-concept. Research by Corrigan (2004) found that individuals who engage in identity integration where they acknowledge their disability but also embrace other

aspects of their identity are better able to maintain high levels of self-esteem. Adolescents who view their disability as a challenge to be managed, rather than a limitation, tend to develop greater self-confidence and a more positive self-image.

Adolescents with disabilities experience a wide range of challenges and opportunities in shaping their self-image. While negative self-image can arise from societal stigma, negative peer interactions, and lack of family support, positive self-image can develop through resilience, supportive peer relationships, family encouragement, and the integration of their disability into their identity. By fostering inclusive environments, promoting self-advocacy, and encouraging positive family dynamics, it is possible to support adolescents with disabilities in developing a positive self-image that enables them to thrive during this critical period of development.

Objective Two: impact of social, cultural and institutional factors on self image of adolescent with visible disabilities

Social factors have a profound impact on the self-image of adolescents with disabilities. These factors include interactions with peers, family dynamics, societal attitudes, and the broader social environment in which these adolescents live. Social influences play a central role in shaping how adolescents with disabilities perceive their own worth, capabilities, and place in society.

Adolescence is a critical time for the development of social identity, and peer relationships are especially influential. Adolescents with disabilities often face social challenges, including exclusion, bullying, and stereotyping due to their disabilities. According to Polloway et al. (2010), negative peer interactions can severely damage self-esteem and lead to feelings of inferiority and isolation. Adolescents with disabilities may internalize these negative experiences, resulting in low self-worth and social withdrawal. For example, a teenager with a visible disability might be teased or excluded from social groups, leading them to feel unworthy of acceptance (Sharma et al., 2012). This type of rejection can create a negative self-image, where the adolescent begins to see themselves as less valuable or capable compared to their peers. Conversely, positive peer relationships and inclusion can have a strong positive impact on self-esteem. Inclusive interactions, where adolescents with disabilities are valued and accepted, help reinforce their sense of belonging and self-worth (Siperstein et al., 2011). Acceptance by peers fosters social confidence and a more positive view of oneself.

The family is one of the most important social influences in an adolescent's life, particularly in shaping their self-concept. A supportive family that encourages independence and fosters a positive outlook can enhance self-esteem and self-image in adolescents with disabilities. According to McConachie and Randle (2007), families that are emotionally supportive help adolescents with disabilities develop resilience and a positive sense of self. These families encourage their children to engage in activities, pursue their goals, and see their disability as just one part of their identity, not as something that limits their potential. However, family members' attitudes toward disability can also have a negative impact on self-image. Families that are overly protective or that view disability solely as a problem may inadvertently reinforce feelings of inadequacy and helplessness. Murphy et al. (2014) found that when parents are overly cautious or set low expectations, adolescents with disabilities may begin to feel that they are incapable of achieving success or independence. In contrast, when families encourage self-sufficiency and see their child's disability as part of their individuality, adolescents are more likely to develop a positive self-image.

Societal attitudes toward disability heavily influence the way adolescents with disabilities perceive themselves. In many societies, people with disabilities are marginalized, and there are negative stereotypes associated with disability, such as assumptions of incompetence, dependency, or being a burden. These societal attitudes can lead adolescents with disabilities to internalize stigma, creating a negative self-concept (Corrigan & Watson, 2003). Visible disabilities make adolescents more susceptible to such stigma because they cannot easily hide their condition. As Goffman (1963) explains, individuals with visible disabilities often face the challenge of managing a "spoiled identity," meaning they are seen as less worthy or capable than others. This societal bias can lead adolescents to feel alienated or "othered," diminishing their self-worth. However, when societal attitudes are more inclusive and positive, adolescents with disabilities can develop stronger, healthier self-images. Positive portrayals of disability in the media and social movements advocating for disability rights can help challenge these stereotypes, creating a more supportive environment for adolescents to develop a positive self-concept (Shakespeare, 2006).

Social integration in educational and recreational activities plays a significant role in shaping the self-image of adolescents with disabilities. Inclusion in social groups, extracurricular activities, and school events allows adolescents to feel like they belong, which is essential for healthy self-esteem. According to research by Polloway et al. (2010), adolescents with disabilities who experience social inclusion in schools tend to have better self-esteem than those who are excluded or segregated. Inclusive environments help these adolescents develop a sense of normalcy, reinforcing their identity as capable and equal members of society. On the other hand, exclusion and isolation from peers can result in feelings of inadequacy and social rejection. When adolescents are excluded from activities or face discrimination, it can lead to negative self-perceptions, as they may come to believe that they are unworthy of inclusion or acceptance (Lipsky

& Gartner, 1997). Therefore, creating inclusive environments where adolescents with disabilities can participate fully and equally is essential for fostering a positive self-image.

Support from social networks both familial and peer-based is crucial in shaping the self-image of adolescents with disabilities. Strong social support networks provide the necessary emotional and psychological resilience to deal with challenges and adversity. As noted by Siperstein et al. (2011), adolescents with disabilities who receive encouragement and validation from their families and peers tend to have more positive self-images. The support they receive helps counteract the negative impact of exclusion and societal stigma, providing adolescents with the confidence to pursue their goals and interact with others without fear of judgment. In contrast, the absence of social support, or having a network that reinforces negative stereotypes about disability, can lead to poor mental health and low self-esteem. Adolescents who lack a supportive social environment may feel isolated and unsupported, leading to difficulties in forming a positive self-concept (Sharma et al., 2012). Social factors, including peer interactions, family dynamics, societal attitudes, and social inclusion, all play crucial roles in shaping the self-image of adolescents with disabilities. Negative social experiences, such as exclusion, bullying, or stigma, can lead to low self-esteem and a negative self-concept. However, positive social support, inclusive environments, and supportive family dynamics can foster a strong sense of self-worth and confidence. To support the positive self-image of adolescents with disabilities, it is essential to create inclusive and supportive social environments that challenge stereotypes and provide opportunities for social integration.

Cultural factors significantly influence how adolescents with disabilities perceive themselves, as cultural attitudes, values, and beliefs shape the way disability is understood and experienced in society. These factors can either enhance or hinder the development of a positive self-image. Societal views on disability, cultural representations in media, and the cultural context in which adolescents grow up all impact their self-concept and self-esteem. This discussion will explore the various ways in which cultural factors affect the self-image of adolescents with disabilities.

Cultural attitudes toward disability play a central role in shaping how adolescents with disabilities view themselves. In some cultures, disability is seen as a source of shame or something to be hidden, which can lead to a negative self-concept for adolescents. As Shakespeare (2006) explains, in many societies, there is a tendency to view disability as an unfortunate or tragic condition that limits an individual's potential. Adolescents in these cultural contexts may internalize such negative views, leading them to feel inferior or disconnected from their peers. For example, in some parts of the world, people with disabilities are viewed as burdens or as less capable, which can foster feelings of inadequacy in adolescents who grow up in such environments. Conversely, other cultures may have more inclusive and positive attitudes toward disability, viewing it as a natural part of human diversity. In these cultures, individuals with disabilities are often respected and valued for their unique perspectives and contributions. The social model of disability, which emphasizes the removal of societal barriers rather than focusing on the individual's limitations, is more prominent in these cultures (Oliver, 1996). For adolescents raised in such cultural contexts, the experience of being disabled may not be as stigmatizing, and they may be more likely to develop a positive self-image and see themselves as valued members of their communities.

In some cultures, disability is integrated into the broader cultural identity, and individuals with disabilities may be viewed as having specific roles or responsibilities within their communities. For example, in some Indigenous cultures, disability is not seen as a limitation but as an aspect of identity that brings unique skills or insight. This cultural acceptance can lead adolescents to view their disability as an integral part of who they are, contributing to a strong sense of self-worth. According to Mitchell and Snyder (2015), many Indigenous cultures have longstanding traditions of accommodating and respecting individuals with disabilities, which can foster resilience and pride. On the other hand, in cultures that view disability as something "other" or as an impediment to normal life, adolescents with disabilities may struggle to reconcile their disability with their cultural identity. This dissonance can result in confusion, shame, and a sense of alienation, leading to negative self-perceptions. For example, in cultures where there is an emphasis on physical ability and success, an adolescent with a visible disability may feel that they do not meet these cultural ideals, leading them to feel less valued or capable (Shakespeare, 2006).

Family dynamics and cultural expectations also shape adolescents' self-perception. In many cultures, families have a significant influence on how adolescents view their disabilities. In some cultures, there may be pressure on adolescents with disabilities to "overcome" their condition and achieve conventional success. This pressure can lead to feelings of inadequacy if adolescents feel they are not meeting cultural expectations. For example, in cultures that prioritize academic or physical achievement, an adolescent with a disability may feel that they are failing to live up to societal ideals (Murphy et al, 2014). On the other hand, families that view disability as part of the natural human experience, rather than something to be hidden or overcome, can foster a more positive self-image in adolescents. Research has shown that family support and acceptance of a child's disability contribute significantly to higher self-esteem (McConachie & Randle, 2007). In cultures where families are more accepting and supportive, adolescents with disabilities are more likely to develop a positive self-concept and feel proud of who they are. Cultural factors, including

cultural attitudes toward disability, family expectations, media representations, and the broader cultural context, all play critical roles in shaping the self-image of adolescents with disabilities. In cultures where disability is stigmatized or viewed negatively, adolescents may struggle with feelings of inadequacy and alienation. Conversely, in cultures that celebrate disability as part of human diversity, adolescents are more likely to develop a positive self-concept. Positive media portrayals and supportive family environments further enhance self-esteem, while negative cultural representations can reinforce stereotypes and hinder self-image. Therefore, it is essential to create culturally inclusive environments that recognize and value the diversity of experiences among adolescents with disabilities.

Institutional factors, including the policies, structures, and practices within educational, healthcare, and social systems, significantly influence the self-image of adolescents with disabilities. These institutional factors can either support or hinder the development of a positive self-concept for adolescents with disabilities, affecting their overall well-being, self-esteem, and sense of belonging. Institutional support, inclusive policies, and accessibility to necessary resources are critical in helping these adolescents develop a healthy self-image, while discriminatory practices, exclusion, and lack of adequate accommodations can negatively impact their sense of self-worth. Below, we will explore how various institutional factors influence the self-image of adolescents with disabilities.

The school environment plays a central role in shaping the self-image of adolescents with disabilities, as education is a major context in which they develop social and academic identities. The extent to which schools are inclusive, accommodating, and supportive directly impacts how adolescents with disabilities perceive themselves. Inclusive education where students with disabilities are integrated into general education classrooms and have access to the same resources and opportunities as their non-disabled peers has been shown to promote a positive self-image among adolescents with disabilities (Bunch & Valeo, 2004). According to Polloway et al. (2010), students with disabilities who are included in mainstream educational settings tend to have higher self-esteem and a more positive self-concept because they feel valued and accepted by their peers and teachers. Conversely, segregation in special education classes can have a negative impact on adolescents' self-image. Research by Lipsky and Gartner (1997) indicates that when students with disabilities are placed in separate classrooms or schools, they may feel excluded and less capable compared to their peers. This isolation can lead to feelings of inferiority, as adolescents with disabilities might internalize societal messages about their worth. For example, a student with a visible disability in a segregated educational setting may feel marginalized or "different," which could hinder the development of a positive self-image. Moreover, limited opportunities for social interaction with non-disabled peers can reinforce feelings of social isolation, reducing adolescents' sense of belonging.

Access to support services and accommodations is another crucial institutional factor affecting adolescents with disabilities. Schools and other institutions that provide necessary accommodations such as assistive technology, modified curriculum, extra time on exams, or physical accessibility can help adolescents with disabilities succeed both academically and socially, leading to a positive self-image (Lipsky & Gartner, 1997). When adolescents with disabilities are given the resources, they need to participate fully in school activities, they are more likely to feel competent, confident, and capable of achieving their goals. The presence of specialized support services, such as counsellors, mentors, or disability advocacy programs, also plays a significant role in helping these adolescents develop resilience and a positive self-concept (McConachie & Randle, 2007). However, the lack of appropriate accommodations or support services can have the opposite effect, leading to frustration, academic underachievement, and negative self-perceptions. Adolescents who are not provided with the tools they need to succeed may feel excluded or incompetent, which can diminish their self-esteem. For example, a student with a learning disability who does not have access to accommodations such as extra time for assignments may feel overwhelmed and incapable, leading to feelings of failure (Sharma et al., 2012). The absence of support systems can exacerbate the sense of alienation, reducing adolescents' confidence and self-worth.

Institutional discrimination and lack of accessibility in educational and public institutions can have a significant negative impact on the self-image of adolescents with disabilities. Goffman (1963) argues that individuals with disabilities often face stigma, which is amplified by institutional practices that marginalize them. Discriminatory attitudes in educational settings, such as low expectations for students with disabilities, can lead to feelings of being "less than" their peers. These attitudes can result in adolescents with disabilities perceiving themselves as inferior, reinforcing negative stereotypes about their abilities. Moreover, physical inaccessibility in schools or public spaces can contribute to feelings of exclusion and social isolation. When adolescents with disabilities are unable to access the same physical spaces as their peers due to lack of ramps, elevators, or accessible restrooms, they may feel that they are being treated as "other" or less valued. Research has shown that the lack of accessibility can result in negative emotional outcomes, including feelings of anger, frustration, and helplessness (Sharma et al., 2012). For example, an adolescent with a wheelchair may have trouble navigating a school that is not wheelchair-accessible, which can reinforce feelings of inferiority and exclusion.

The healthcare system also plays an important role in shaping the self-image of adolescents with disabilities. Adolescents with disabilities often require medical care, therapy, and ongoing treatment to manage their conditions. The way they are

treated within the healthcare system can impact their self-esteem and self-concept. Healthcare professionals who treat adolescents with disabilities with respect and dignity, and who encourage independence and self-advocacy, help foster a positive self-image (Murphy et al, 2014). However, healthcare systems that focus primarily on the limitations or medical "fixes" of disabilities, rather than on the individual's strengths and potential, may inadvertently contribute to negative self-concept and low self-esteem. For example, an adolescent who frequently encounters medical professionals who view their disability as a defect to be "treated" or "corrected" may internalize these views, leading to a diminished sense of self-worth. Alternatively, a healthcare system that promotes a holistic, person-centred approach, emphasizing the adolescent's autonomy, strengths, and goals, can help the adolescent build confidence and see their disability as just one part of their identity (Oliver, 1996). Adolescents who feel empowered by healthcare professionals are more likely to have a positive self-image and a strong sense of identity.

Institutional policies and advocacy efforts can also influence the self-image of adolescents with disabilities. Policies that promote inclusion, equal rights, and accessibility are essential in ensuring that adolescents with disabilities have the same opportunities as their peers. For example, the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) in the United States mandates that public institutions, including schools, provide reasonable accommodations to individuals with disabilities, which can help reduce stigma and promote inclusion (Shakespeare, 2006). When adolescents with disabilities experience positive institutional support through such policies, they are more likely to feel valued and capable. However, the absence of such policies or the enforcement of discriminatory policies can have a detrimental impact on adolescents' self-image. Adolescents who experience barriers due to exclusionary practices may feel powerless and invisible, which can undermine their sense of self-worth and self-esteem. The lack of disability advocacy in certain regions or institutions can also result in a lack of representation and voice for adolescents with disabilities, further contributing to feelings of marginalization (Smith, 2010).

Institutional factors, including inclusive education practices, the availability of support services, discriminatory practices, accessibility, and healthcare systems, all significantly impact the self-image of adolescents with disabilities. Positive institutional environments that provide support, inclusion, and equitable opportunities foster a sense of competence, belonging, and self-worth in adolescents with disabilities. In contrast, exclusionary or discriminatory practices can lead to feelings of isolation, inadequacy, and low self-esteem. To promote positive self-image among adolescents with disabilities, it is essential to implement inclusive policies, ensure accessibility, and provide necessary resources and accommodations in all institutional settings.

Conclusion

The examined the self image of adolescents with visible disabilities in Buea municipality and found that self-perception among this group is shaped by a complex interplay of social, familial, institutional and cultural factors. While some adolescents exhibited resilience and a positive sense of self, many others reported experiences of low self esteem social exclusion and internalised stigma. The quality of social interactions particularly peer relationships family support and school inclusion played a significant role in shaping how these adolescents view themselves. The findings underscore the urgent need to address societal attitudes and systems barriers that negatively impact psychosocial development of adolescents with visible disabilities. The study recommends that

- Schools should introduce awareness programs to reduce stigma and foster empathy among students which will promote positive peer relationships and a positive self image
- The implementation of inclusive policies should be reinforced in most institutions
- The provision of targeted psychosocial interventions to improve the self image and overall well-being of this vulnerable population is of ought most importance.

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